

CLASSIFICATION OF HONORIFICS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. In this article, the various honorific titles in English and their specific addresses are fully described in whom and in which case they are reflected.

Keywords: honorific system, politeness category, honorific references, titular, titles.

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ПОЧЕТНЫХ МЕТОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. В этой статье полностью описаны различные почетные титулы на английском языке и их конкретные адреса, в ком и в каком случае они отражены.

Ключевые слова: почетная система, категория вежливости, почетные обращения, титуляр, титулы.

Honorifics have currently occupied an important position within the domain of socio-pragmatic studies of language and within the theories of communication. Honorifics are derived from outputs of politeness strategies where these directly or indirectly convey a status deferential between speaker and addressee or referent, where they indirectly convey such a status deferential, as in French Tu / Vous pronouns do via the general strategy of pluralizing in order to impersonalize¹.

Honorifics have been defined as “politeness formulas in a particular language which may be specific affixes, words, or sentence structure”². Languages which have a complex system of honorifics are, for instance, Japanese, Mudurese (a language of Eastern Java), Hindi, and Arabic; English, on the other hand, has no complex system of honorifics, but there are few cases of compound honorifics; e.g. *professor doctor*, *dear sir*, etc.³

J.T. Irvine points out that “linguistic honorifics are forms of speech that signal social deference, through conventionalized understandings of some aspects, of the form meaning relationship”⁴.

From this brief account of the concept of honorifics, we may define it as linguistic or non-linguistic means or device that can function to convey social deference or respect influenced by the dimension of power and solidarity.

The honorifics can be divided into two main types: **referential honorifics** and **absolute honorifics**. In the rest of the chapter, we want to provide information about the use of these types in English and Uzbek. Let's first think about the division of Honorifics into these types and features of use in English.

¹Brown P. and Levinson S. (1978): “Universals In Language Usage”. In: E.N. Goody (ed.), Questions and Politeness: Strategies in Social Interaction. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. – P.183. (pp 56-289.)

²Richard J. Platt J. and Weber. H. (1985): Longman Dictionary of Applied Linguistics. – London: Longman Group Ltd. – P.131.

³Ibid.: P.131.

⁴Irvine J. T. (1995): “Honorifics”. In: J. Verschueren et al. (eds.), Handbook of Pragmatics. – Amsterdam, Philadelphia: John Benjamins. – P.1. (pp 1-22.)

Referential Honorifics

Honorifics are grammatical forms utilized in speaking to express social superiority. The part of speech affected is different from one language to another, and the honorifics may be distinguishable from simply very polite forms used in formal address. In many languages they affect the pronouns: in French, “*Vous*” is used rather than “*Tu*”; in Uzbek, we use the pronoun “*siz*” rather than the familiar one “*sen*” in addressing a single person. Honorifics seem most highly developed in certain oriental languages, such as Japanese and Korean⁵.

A. Agha claims that the use of honorifics in all communities is governed by the social status of persons to whom deference is paid, but it is also sensitive to interactional variables⁶. With regard to status, the general norm: the higher the status, the greater the degree of deference.

M. Farghal and A. Shakir view social honorifics “as the encoding of social information in human interaction. Such information is manifest in the use of pronouns and titles of address”⁷.

The view of honorifics as directed indexes of context seems unable to account for the complexity and diversity of actual uses of honorifics adequately. For example, the treatment of honorifics as status difference markers cannot explain their reciprocal use, despite the fact that honorifics are generally used by a person of a higher status to a person of a lower status; this treatment in addition to that, must assume that in the non-reciprocal use of honorifics not only honorific form but also non-honorific forms are markers of status differences. On the other hand, the treatment of honorifics as markers of non-intimate relationships cannot account for the nonreciprocal use of honorifics, because it must assume that two individuals perceive the same relationship differently as non-intimate and intimate⁸.

S. Levinson points out that honorifics can be divided into two main types⁹. The first type is called “relational” which is more important than the second one and mainly concerned with the socially deictic information in languages of the world. Within this relational system of honorifics, three subcategories are distinguished; they are addressee honorifics, referent honorifics and bystander honorifics. The second type of honorifics in Levinson’s typology is called “absolute” honorifics which express the relationship between the speaker and the setting through formality levels. Absolute honorifics are categorized into “authorized speakers” and “authorized recipients” according to the perspectives of the speakers and recipients.

Addressee honorifics, as B. Comrie argues, refer to the relationship between the speaker and the hearer¹⁰.

R. Brown and S. Levinson point out that addressee honorifics are direct encodings of the speaker-addressee relationship, independent of the referential content of the utterance¹¹. M.

⁵The New Encyclopedia Britannica, (1980): Vol. V. – Chicago: Encyclopedia Britannica Inc. - P. 115.

⁶Agha A. (1994): “Honorificiation”. In: Annual Review of Anthropology, 23. - P. 294. (pp 277-302.)

⁷Farghal M. and Shakir A. (1994): “Kin Terms and Titles of Address as Relational Social Honorifics in Jordanian Arabic”. In: Anthropological Linguistics, 36. – P. 240. (pp 20-253.)

⁸Okamoto S. (1999): “Situating Politeness: Manipulating Honorific and Non-Honorific Expressions in Japanese Conversations”. In: Pragmatics (IPrA), 9(1). – P.53-54. (pp 51- 74.)

⁹Levinson S. (1983): Pragmatics. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. – P. 90-91.

¹⁰Comrie, B. (1976): “Linguistic Politeness Axes: Speaker-Addressee, Speaker-Referent, Speaker – By – Stander”. In: Pragmatic Microfiche, 1.7: A3. – University of Cambridge, Dept. of Linguistics.

¹¹Brown, P. and Levinson, S. (1978): “Universals In Language Usage”. In: E.N. Goody (ed.), Questions and Politeness: Strategies in Social Interaction. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. – P.276. (pp 56-289.)

Sifianou mentions that this category of honorifics expresses respect to the addressees by choosing particular linguistic items or forms, without directly referring to them¹².

Referent honorifics are those expressions which are used to convey speaker's respect to persons or things actually referred to¹³. In this sense, they are the relational honorifics which express the relations held between the speaker and the referent. R. Brown and A. Gilman's¹⁴ (1960) *Tu/Vous* pronouns distinction in singular pronouns of address is considered as a form of referent honorifics that give respect directly to the hearer.

Besides, other referent honorifics may indirectly express respect to the addressee. In English the second member of pairs like *Snuggs / Dr Snuggs, eat/dine, man/gentleman, give/bestow, book/volume* and so on encode greater respect to the person, activity or thing than others. By using these referent honorifics about something related to the hearer, the speaker as a matter of fact expresses respect to him.

By- Stander Honorifics:

By-stander honorifics are a relational type of honorifics which express the relationship between the speaker and the bystander¹⁵. These honorifics include those cases in which a different set of expressions are utilized in the presence of certain by-standers. In Australian Aboriginal communities, a special speech style, called "mother-in-law" language, is avoided in the presence of certain by-standers, while it is employed by every one when the presence of certain by-standers necessitates the use of special verbal and non-verbal behaviours¹⁶.

The **peerages** in the United Kingdom are a legal system comprising both hereditary and lifetime titles, composed of various noble ranks, and forming a constituent part of the British Honorific system. The term peerage can be used both collectively to refer to the entire body of nobles (or a subdivision thereof), and individually to refer to a specific title (modern English language-style using an initial capital in the latter case but not the former). The Peerage of Great Britain – titles created for the Kingdom of Great Britain between 1707 and 1801.

British nobility, in the United Kingdom, members of the upper social class, who usually possess a hereditary **title**. The titled nobility are part of the peerage, which shares the responsibility of government. The peerage comprises five ranks, which are, in descending order, *duke, marquess, earl, viscount, and baron*. Below the peerage are honorary ranks that include *baronet* and *knight*, two classes that bear similarities to the nobility but which are generally not regarded as such.

In the English language system, we analyze the following title names and their origin (in the example of the United Kingdom):

1. **Monarchy** is a form of government in which a single person, called a monarch, is the head of state for the duration of their life. The word is of Greek origin, deriving from the words "*mono*"

¹²Sifianou, M. (1992): *Politeness Phenomena in England and Greece: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*. – Oxford: Clarendo Press. – P.57.

¹³Sifianou, M. (1992): *Politeness Phenomena in England and Greece: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*. – Oxford: Clarendo Press. – P.57.

¹⁴Brown R. and Gilman A. (1960): "The Pronouns of Power and Solidarity". In: Sebeok (ed.), *Style in Language*. – Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. – pp 253-276.

¹⁵Levinson, S. (1983): *Pragmatics*. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. – P. 90.

¹⁶Sifianou, M. (1992): *Politeness Phenomena in England and Greece: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*. – Oxford: Clarendo Press. – P.57.

(one) and "archy" (rule). The system of nobility in the United Kingdom is known as the peerage, and has been developed over more than a thousand years since the time of the Anglo-Saxons.

2. **King** is the title given to a male monarch in a variety of contexts. The English term *king* is derived from the Anglo-Saxon "cynning", which in turn is derived from the Common Germanic "kuningaz". The Common Germanic term was borrowed into Estonian and Finnish at an early time, surviving in these languages as *kuningas*. It is a derivation from the term *kunjom* "kin" (Old English *cynn*) by the *-inga-* suffix. The literal meaning is that of a "scion of the [noble] kin", or perhaps "son or descendant of one of noble birth". The English term translates, and is considered equivalent to, Latin *rēx* and its equivalents in the various European languages. The Germanic term is notably different from the word for "King" in other Indo-European languages (*rēks* "ruler"; Latin *rēx*, Sanskrit *rājan* and Irish *ríg*; however, see Gothic *reiks* and, e.g., modern German Reich and modern Dutch rijk). The synonym of it: *captain, czar, tsar, tzar, lion, magnate, mogul, monarch, Napoleon, tycoon*.

3. **Queen** a woman who rules a country and who usually inherits her position and rules for life. For eg.:

She was crowned queen of England;
the reign of Queen Elizabeth.

Second meaning of the word "queen" is the wife of a king the king and his queen. For eg.:
the king and his queen.

The other meaning of the word "queen" is a girl or woman who is highly respected and very successful or popular:

She's a fashion queen;
the queen of the blues.

From Middle English *quene, queen, cwen*, from Old English *cwēn* ("queen"), from Proto-West Germanic *kwāni*, from Proto-Germanic *kwēniz* ("woman"), from Proto-Indo-European *gʷéh₂s* ("woman"). Related to and possibly merged with and/or absorbed some senses of English *quean*, from Middle English *quene*, from Old English *cwene* ("woman; female serf, quean"). Generally eclipsed non-native Middle English *regina* ("queen"), borrowed from Latin *rēgīna* ("queen") (Modern English *regina*). Doublet of *quean* and *gyne*. The synonym of this word "queen" is *archduke, aristocracy, aristocrat, master*.

Absolute Honorifics

Every society, considering the importance of the power relations that govern it, enjoys a special system of honorifics. A society with a very advanced system of honorifics shows the importance of superior-inferior and power relations. In contrast, in communities where these issues are not taken into account, a simpler system of honorifics is used.

It is axiomatic that languages mirror the world view of their users. Manipulating honorific forms among people inevitably reflects this truth. Honorifics are conventionalized forms or expressions manifested in all the world's languages and are used to express the social status of the participants in the verbal interaction and to convey indications like politeness and respect. English is no exception. However the question is what exactly creates these forms and their meanings. Although honorifics have been extensively researched from a grammatical and semantic angle, yet they haven't received that significant attention in pragmatic research, especially their use in literary works. Thus, this qualitative paper aims at clarifying the main linguistic devices that

represent English honorific forms and investigating the main functions and the pragmatic meanings that these forms can express.

M.Farghal and A.Shakir argued that it referred to contact of interactors (speaker, interlocutor, and also object of utterance) and their social activities¹⁷. The high line was differences of formality and informality framing the contact of interactors "role and particular situation". There was a certain expression that the actor had to adapt his or her social interaction.

On the other hand, Verschueren gives a more accurate definition; concentrating on the linguistic representatives of honorifics saying "honorifics are language forms such as pronouns, vocative expressions, titles of address and the like, used to encode the high status of the interlocutor"¹⁸.

Absolute honorifics was exclusively limited to someone or something admitted to the social and title of the class, such as "*Your Honour*," "*Professor*," "*Oh God*," and so on. Absolute social honorifics required authorized recipients for whom these titles were reserved. Furthermore, absolute social honorifics might be hugely explained to represent phenomena that were used for social aims such as greetings, "*assalamualaikum*," "*ahlan wasahlan*".

These sets of honorifics refer to the relationship between speaker (and perhaps other participants) and setting (or social activity). What is important here is the distinction between formality and informality which colours the relationship between the participants' roles and situations. As a matter of fact, there are certain forms which are particularly reserved for certain speakers and other forms which are reserved for certain recipients. The first sets of forms are used by "authorized speakers", for example the form of the first person pronoun is specifically reserved for the use of the Japanese Emperor. The second set of forms is particularly received by "authorized recipients"¹⁹.

Farghal and Shakir view that the absolute social honorifics are certain forms reserved for authorized speakers and recipients²⁰. For example, in Arabic the use of the first person plural (نحن) "we" by the king of Jordan in royal ordinances is an absolute honorific exclusively restricted to him as the only authorized speaker who can speak on behalf of his people, while the use of titles of address, such as "*Your Honour*", "*His Majesty*", "*Professor*", etc. are absolute social honorifics requiring authorized recipients for whom these titles are reserved. Furthermore, absolute social honorifics may be expanded to cover many phenomena that are primarily used for social aims such as greetings e.g. (مرحباً - حُصِّبْتُ) and politeness markers e.g. (لطفاً) (among others. Such examples of social honorifics should be remarked as non-authorized in nature, i.e., they do not require authorized speakers and recipients. For example, on an absolute scale of Politeness, the examples on the right side of the arrow are more polite than those of the left. Consider the following:

1) *Help me* → *Help me, will/can you?* → *Can you help me?* → *Could you possibly help me?*

¹⁷Farghal M. and Shakir A. "Kin Terms and Titles of Address as Relational Social Honorifics in Jordanian Arabic" // In: Anthropological Linguistics, 36,1994. - P.241. (pp 20-253.)

¹⁸Verschueren Jef. Understanding Pragmatics. - London: Arnold, 1992. – P.21.

¹⁹Levinson, S. (1983): Pragmatics. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. – P.91.

²⁰Farghal, M. and Shakir, A. (1994): "Kin Terms and Titles of Address as Relational Social Honorifics in Jordanian Arabic". In: Anthropological Linguistics, 36, - P.241. (pp. 20-253.)

(2) *Thanks* → *Thank you very much.*

(3) *Name, please* → *What's your name, please* → *Can you tell me your name please?* → *Could you possibly tell me your name, please?* (→ *I wonder if you could tell me your name.*)

So, we can say, an honorific is a form of address conveying esteem, courtesy or respect in the English language²¹. These can be titles prefixing a person's name, e.g.: *Mr, Mrs, Miss, Ms, Mx, Sir, Dame, Dr, Cllr, Lady* or *Lord*, or titles or positions that can appear as a form of address without the person's name, as in *Mr President, General, Captain, Father, Doctor* or *Earl*. Many forms of honorifics are for members of the nobility, clergy, military/naval forces, or royalty, mostly in countries that are monarchies. These include "*Your Majesty*", "*Your Royal Highness*" or simply "*Your Highness*", which are used to address certain members of royalty and "*My lord/lady*" or "*Your Lordship/Ladyship*" to address a peer other than a Duke, who is referred to as "*Your Grace*".

If any, scholars have paid more attention to the pragmatic strategy of showing Politeness in the case of English. For example, Brown & Levinson (1987) have proposed their analyses and proposals, and their research has been used as pivots for Politeness/Impoliteness studies rather than the manifestations of Honorifics in English²².

Using honorific intend to charm of the social strata of communication and to attract attention find respect from the other person. An honorific can reduce the risk of conflict and strengthen cohesion in the society concerned. Furthermore, honorifics are typically used to humble themselves and elevate the listener. The hearer person will feel positioned in a position or status honorifics when applied correctly²³. On the other hand, the fact that legislature members are often expressed in the form of interrogative speech to ask for clarification about the executive or the public action. The use of interrogative forms as part of an indirect speech-oriented pattern of modesty.

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